

Guia Básico para Uso do Biblioshiny

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1. Objetivos do material

- Instalação dos softwares R
- Importação do arquivo para o Biblioshiny
- Apresentação das principais análises realizadas pelo software, incluindo as estatísticas descritivas de dados obtidos junto aos artigos para fins de análise bibliométrica

2. Referências de artigos sobre revisão sistemática

2.1 Exemplos de artigos de análise bibliométrica e revisão sistemática que usam o Biblioshiny

Artigo 1 – Shome, S., Hassan, M. K., Verma, S., & Panigrahi, T. R. (2023). Impact investment for sustainable development: A bibliometric analysis. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 84, 770-800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2022.12.001>

Artigo 2 – Cosma, S., Rimo, G., & Cosma, S. (2023). Conservation finance: What are we not doing? A review and research agenda. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 336, 117649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117649>

Artigo 3 – Sharma, G. D., Verma, M., Shahbaz, M., Gupta, M., & Chopra, R. (2022). Transitioning green finance from theory to practice for renewable energy development. *Renewable Energy*, 195, 554-565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.06.041>

Artigo 4 - Khan, M. A. (2022). ESG disclosure and firm performance: A bibliometric and meta analysis. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 61, 101668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2022.101668>

2.2 Referência de artigo sobre o pacote Bibliometrix

Artigo 5 - Aria, M. & Cuccurullo, C. (2017) bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959-975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>

3. Instalação do software R

3.1 Baixe e instale a versão mais recente do R, clicando em <https://cran.r-project.org>

3.2 Clicar em Download R for Windows

Download and Install R

Precompiled binary distributions of the base system and contributed packages, **Windows and Mac** users most likely want one of these versions of R:

- [Download R for Linux](#)
- [Download R for \(Mac\) OS X](#)
- [Download R for Windows](#)

3.3 Clicar em Install R for the first time

R for Windows

Subdirectories:

- [base](#)
- [contrib](#)
- [old contrib](#)
- [Rtools](#)

Binaries for base distribution. This is what you want to [install R for the first time](#).

Binaries of contributed CRAN packages (for R >= 3.4.x).

Binaries of contributed CRAN packages for outdated versions of R (for R < 3.4.x).

Tools to build R and R packages. This is what you want to build your own packages on Windows, or to build R itself.

3.4 Clicar em Download R 4.2.3 for Windows (77 megabytes, 64 bit)

R-4.2.3 for Windows

[Download R-4.2.3 for Windows](#) (77 megabytes, 64 bit)

[README on the Windows binary distribution](#)

[New features in this version](#)

This build requires UCRT, which is part of Windows since Windows 10 and Windows Server 2016. On older systems, UCRT has to be installed manually from [here](#).

If you want to double-check that the package you have downloaded matches the package distributed by CRAN, you can compare the [md5sum](#) of the .exe to the [file's md5sum](#) on the master server.

3.5 Acesso ao Biblioshiny no ambiente web a partir do R

Instalação dos pacotes básicos do R e Bibliometrix

```
install.packages("openxlsx")
```

Obs: Se o sistema perguntar: Would you like to use a personal library instead? Clique em YES e depois escolha a opção Brazil (SP 1) [https] e Clicar em OK

```
install.packages("bibliometrix")
library("bibliometrix")
biblioshiny()
```

```

RGui (64-bit) - [R Console]
Arquivo Editar Visualizar Misc Pacotes Janelas Ajuda
[Icons]

> Database<-mergeDbSources(M,W, remove.duplicated = TRUE)

53 duplicated documents have been removed
> View (Database)
> dim(Database)
[1] 186 28
>
> library(openxlsx)
>
> write.xlsx(Database, file = "Database.xlsx")
> biblioshiny()
Carregando pacotes exigidos: shiny

```

Obs: Deve abrir a seguinte página no seu ambiente web:

4. Informações iniciais sobre o Biblioshiny

4.1 Como usar o Biblioshiny

Please follow the biblioshiny tutorial at:

www.bibliometrix.org/biblioshiny

<http://www.bibliometrix.org/biblioshiny/assets/player/KeynoteDHTMLPlayer.html#0>

https://www.bibliometrix.org/vignettes/Introduction_to_bibliometrix.html

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9YwVhFEovCA>

O Biblioshiny é um aplicativo que fornece uma interface da web para bibliometrix.

Ele apoia os estudiosos no uso fácil dos principais recursos do bibliometrix:

o Importação de dados e conversão para coleta de quadro de dados

o Coleta de dados usando Dimensions, PubMed e coleta de APIs Scopus

- o Filtragem de dados
- o Analytics e Plots para três métricas de nível diferentes:
 - Fontes
 - Autores
 - Documentos
- o Análise de três estruturas de conhecimento (estruturas K):
 - Estrutura Conceitual
 - Estrutura Intelectual
 - Estrutura Social

4.2 Alguns conceitos importantes

Global Citations (TC) means the Total Citations that an article, included in your collection, has received from documents indexed on a bibliographic database (WoS, Scopus, etc.). So, TC counts citations received by a selected article "all over the world".

In **Most Cited References**, Bibliometrix counts the local citations, in other words, the citations that a reference (a document included in, at least, one of the bibliographies of the articles in your collection) has received from documents included in your collection.

The reference lists include all documents from bibliographies as then many of the references could not be part of your collection! When a reference is also part of your collection, it is called "Cited document".

So, **Local citations** are citations received by a reference article "internally to your collection".

- A cited document is a document cited by other document of the same collection
- It belongs both in the Document Set and in the Reference Set

Data frame columns are named using the standard Clarivate Analytics WoS Field Tag codify:

Field Tag	Description
AU	Authors
TI	Document Title
SO	Publication Name (or Source)
J1	ISO Source Abbreviation
DT	Document Type
DE	Authors' Keywords

ID	Keywords associated by SCOPUS or ISI database
AB	Abstract
C1	Author Address
RP	Reprint Address
CR	Cited References
TC	Times Cited
PY	Year
SC	Subject Category
UT	Unique Article Identifier
DB	Bibliographic Database

An object of class “bibliometrix” is a list containing the following components:

List element	Description
Articles	the total number of manuscripts
Authors	the authors’ frequency distribution
AuthorsFrac	the authors’ frequency distribution (fractionalized)
FirstAuthors	corresponding author of each manuscript
nAUpperPaper	the number of authors per manuscript
Appearances	the number of author appearances
nAuthors	the number of authors
AuMultiAuthoredArt	the number of authors of multi-authored articles
MostCitedPapers	the list of manuscripts sorted by citations
Years	publication year of each manuscript
FirstAffiliation	the affiliation of the corresponding author
Affiliations	the frequency distribution of affiliations (of all co-authors for each paper)
Aff_frac	the fractionalized frequency distribution of affiliations (of all co-authors for each paper)
CO	the affiliation country of the corresponding author
Countries	the affiliation countries’ frequency distribution
CountryCollaboration	the intra-country (SCP) and inter-country (MCP) collaboration indices
TotalCitation	the number of times each manuscript has been cited
TCperYear	the yearly average number of times each manuscript has been cited
Sources	the frequency distribution of sources (journals, books, etc.)
DE	the frequency distribution of authors’ keywords
ID	the frequency distribution of keywords associated to the manuscript by SCOPUS and Thomson Reuters’ ISI Web of Knowledge databases

5. Importação da base de dados – arquivo Database.xlsx

Na página do Biblioshiny da internet, seguir esses comandos, clicando em:

Data / Load data / Import or Load: Load bibliometrix file(s) / Choose a file: Importar o arquivo.xlsx – **ex: Database** / Start

Obs: Esse arquivo Database foi obtido a partir dos critérios de pesquisa apresentados na Aula 3 sobre ANÁLISE BIBLIOMÉTRICA/REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA que ocorreu no dia 27/04/2023. O tema de pesquisa refere-se à ESG and “financial performance” e os anos de análise são 2021 e 2022.

Completeness of bibliographic metadata

Metadata	Description	Missing Counts	Missing %	Status
C1	Affiliation	0	0.00	Excellent
AU	Author	0	0.00	Excellent
DT	Document Type	0	0.00	Excellent
SO	Journal	0	0.00	Excellent
LA	Language	0	0.00	Excellent
TI	Title	0	0.00	Excellent
TC	Total Citation	0	0.00	Excellent
AB	Abstract	1	0.54	Good
DE	Keywords	1	0.54	Good
RP	Corresponding Author	4	2.15	Good
DI	DOI	5	2.69	Good
PY	Publication Year	9	4.84	Good
ID	Keywords Plus	78	41.94	Poor
CR	Cited References	94	50.54	Critical
NR	Number of Cited References	186	100.00	Completely missing
WC	Science Categories	186	100.00	Completely missing

[Advice](#)
[Save](#)
[Close](#)

The screenshot shows the Biblioshiny web interface. The main area displays a table of bibliometric data with columns: DOI, AU, DE, ID, C1, JI, AB, AR, and RP. The table contains three rows of data, each representing a different document. The left sidebar contains navigation options: biblioshiny, Data, Load Data, Gathering Data, Filters, Overview, Sources, Authors, Documents, Clustering, Conceptual Structure, Intellectual Structure, Social Structure, Report, and Settings. The right sidebar has sections for 'Import or Load' (with options to load a file or choose a file), 'Conversion results' (showing 186 documents), and 'Export collection' (with a 'Save as:' dropdown).

6. Exemplos de análises do Biblioshiny

Na barra azul à esquerda, escolher os tipos de análise desejadas pelos seguintes critérios: Overview, Sources, Authors, Documents, Clustering, Conceptual Structure, Intellectual Structure, Social Structure. Dica: **Após escolher a análise, clicar em Run, quando indicado.**

6.1 Overview

Overview / Main information / Plot

The screenshot shows the 'Main Information' dashboard in Biblioshiny. The dashboard is organized into a grid of blue boxes, each representing a different metric. The metrics are: Timespan (2021:2023), Sources (93), Documents (186), Annual Growth Rate (-31.49%), Authors (457), Authors of single-authored docs (17), International Co-Authorship (20.97%), Co-Authors per Doc (2.76), Author's Keywords (DE) (600), References (5492), Document Average Age (1.15), and Average citations per doc (9.812). The left sidebar is the same as in the previous screenshot, and the top navigation bar is also visible.

Overview / Main information / Table

Main Information

Show 50 rows ▾ Copy CSV Excel PDF Print Search:

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2021:2023
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	93
Documents	186
Annual Growth Rate %	-31.49
Document Average Age	1.15
Average citations per doc	9.812
References	5492
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	430
Author's Keywords (DE)	600
AUTHORS	
Authors	457
Authors of single-authored docs	17
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	22
Co-Authors per Doc	2.76
International co-authorships %	20.97
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	177
article; early access	9

Showing 1 to 21 of 21 entries Previous 1 Next

Overview / Annual Scientific Production / Table

Annual Scientific Production

Show 10 rows ▾ Copy CSV Excel PDF Print Search:

Year	Articles
2021	49
2022	105
2023	23

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries Previous 1 Next

Overview / Average Citations Per Year/ Table

Average Citations Per Year

Show 10 rows ▾ Copy CSV Excel PDF Print Search:

Year	MeanTCperArt	N	MeanTCperYear	CitableYears
2021	18.9	49.00	6.30	3
2022	7.53	105.00	3.77	2
2023	3.17	23.00	3.17	1

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries Previous 1 Next

6.2 Análise dos periódicos - Sources

Sources / Most Relevant Sources

Sources / Most Local Cited Sources

Sources / **Bradford's Law**

Sources / Source Local Impact

Obs: Local citations are citations received by a reference article "internally to your collection".

6.3 Análise dos autores - Authors

Authors / Most Relevant Authors

Authors / Most Local Cited Authors

Authors / Authors' Production over Time

Authors / Lotka's Law

Authors / Author's Impact

Authors/ Affiliations / Most Relevant Affiliations

Authors/ Affiliations / Affiliations' Production over Time

Authors / Countries / Corresponding Author's Country

Obs: CountryCollaboration: the intra-country (SCP) and inter-country (MCP) collaboration indices

Authors / Countries / Country Scientific Production

Authors / Countries / Countries' Production over Time

Authors / Countries / Most Cited Countries

6.4 Análise dos artigos - documents

Documents / Most Global Cited Documents

Obs: Artigos da amostra citados por outros artigos fora da amostra

Documents / Most Local Cited Documents

Obs: Artigos da amostra citados por outros artigos da amostra

Documents / Cited References / Most Local Cited References

Obs: Referências mencionadas nos artigos da amostra citadas pelos artigos da amostra

Documents / Reference Spectroscopy

Obs: Espectroscopia das referências – Apresenta a evolução e concentração cronológica das referências mencionas nos artigos da amostra

Marx, W., Bornmann, L., Barth, A., & Leydesdorff, L. (2014). *Detecting the historical roots of research fields by reference publication year spectroscopy (RPYS)*. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65(4), 751-764. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23089>

Documents / Words / Most Frequent Words

Conceptual Structure / Network approach / Thematic Map / Network

Conceptual Structure / Factorial Approach/ Factorial Analysis / Word map

7.2 Intellectual Structure

Intellectual structure / Co-citation Network

Intellectual structure / Historiograph

7.3 Social structure

Social structure / Collaboration Network

Social structure / Countries' Collaboration World Map

